

AN SHF/EHF FIELD-TO-WIRE COUPLING MODEL
ENHANCEMENT TO IEMCAP

by

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Abstract

This paper will describe an SHF/EHF field-to-wire coupling model enhancement to the Intrasystem Electromagnetic Compatibility Analysis Program (IEMCAP) and provide a comparison of the enhanced and previous versions of IEMCAP. IEMCAP is a widely used code for the intrasystem EMC modeling of spacecraft, aircraft and ground systems [1]. Included in its analysis routines is a coupling model for an external field incident upon a wire over a ground plane. The previous IEMCAP model incorporates a bounding algorithm based on transmission line theory. High frequencies or large distances above the ground plane cause the transmission line model to break down. As a result, RADC funded an effort, under contract F30602-86-0141, to develop a new model for IEMCAP to handle field-to-wire coupling from 1 GHz through 40 GHz [2]. This new model incorporates the results of experimental shielding measurements performed in a mode tuned reverberation chamber and method-of-moments calculations. The new algorithms have been implemented in a modular manner and provide a smooth transition with the previous low frequency IEMCAP predictions. Comparisons between the previous field-to-wire results and the enhanced algorithm results show that the new field-to-wire calculations are much less conservative. However, they match well with measured data.

Introduction

The program to build an SHF/EHF field-to-wire coupling model included four phases; the development of a fast running analytical model for bare wire coupling based on a survey of method-of-moments calculations; an experimental survey and empirical model development of shielding effectiveness for cables and twisted pairs; an experimental verification of the derived models; and the incorporation of this model into the current version of IEMCAP. The new field-to-wire model in IEMCAP calculates a bare wire current value based on method-of-moment trends for frequencies above 1 GHz and, depending upon various wire characteristics, the current is reduced by a shielding effectiveness factor. These steps have culminated in the development and

implementation of a new algorithm that significantly enhances the capability and credibility of field-to-wire coupling in the SHF/EHF region.

Model Development

IEMCAP transmission line theory predicts a coupled current that is linearly proportional to the height above the ground plane. This model is found to significantly overpredict the magnitude of the coupled current when used outside the region where transmission line theory is strictly valid, that is, for small heights above the ground plane. The new bare wire model was derived by empirically modeling the results of a wide variety of method-of-moments calculations for a wire above a ground plane. An upper bound to the induced current was developed by surveying method-of-moments predictions for a variety of wire lengths, separation distances, radii, and termination impedances. The height above the ground plane and impedance were the most sensitive parameters. The maximum coupled current was found to saturate at heights above the ground plane greater than one half wavelength and the saturation level scales as the reciprocal of frequency. Figure 1 shows a comparison of a transmission line code prediction and a method-of-moments computation as a function of height above the ground plane, which demonstrates this saturation effect. Empirical models incorporating these results, were constructed to characterize the magnitude of the coupled current. Once the bare wire coupled current has been predicted, the effective shielding is considered.

A wide variety of experimental parameters were surveyed in the data acquisition phase of the shielding model development. Wire types (coaxial cables and twisted pairs), shielding (single and double shields), wire length, and port termination conditions were examined. Figure 2 depicts the experimental test tree for the cable survey. The dotted lines following the primed nodes indicate that the subsequent parameters are a repeat of the parameters that are beneath the unprimed node of the same order. The experiments outlined in this tree represent only the initial parameters that were explored. As trends in the data became apparent, additional testing was required to unambiguously confirm the trends.

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Excitation: ENDFIRE Length: 22.34 cm Polarization: Vertical
 Loading: 50 ohms Radius: 0.039 cm Ref. Frequency: 1.25 GHz

Figure 1. Field-to-Bare-Wire Coupling Sensitivity to Wire Separation.

Figure 2. Cable Experiment Parameter Tree.

The experimental survey of "shielding effectiveness" in a mode tuned reverberation chamber showed that the cable type and termination condition were important. The results of the experimental program supported a "shielding effectiveness" that was insensitive to cable length but showed a significant sensitivity to the existence of an exposed center conductor. Neither the port termination impedance nor the pigtail length were important. The primary variables were how far away from the receiver port the coupling took place and whether the incident field could couple into an exposed portion of the center conductor. The data supported a model that incorporated a "shielding effectiveness" built upon the behavior of grounded circumferentially bonded cables and propagation transmission loss models.

Field-to-Wire Coupling Mechanisms

Field-to-wire coupling can occur by way of two mechanisms. The first mechanism is coupling "through-

the-shield" and can be represented by a "shielding effectiveness" applied to the bare wire coupled current. Figure 3 shows this "shielding effectiveness" for a single and double shielded coaxial cable. The "shielding effectiveness" is referenced to the coupling for an unshielded bare center conductor.

The second mechanism is the direct coupling to a portion of the shielded cable that has an exposed center conductor. An example of this is a pigtail at the junction of the cable and connector. If any portion of the center conductor is exposed, then the coupling is similar to that for a bare wire. However, the location of the exposed center conductor, relative to the port of interest, is important. If the exposed center conductor is at the receiver port, then the cable will exhibit no shielding. If the exposed center conductor is at the port away from the receiver, then the coupled power is attenuated as it propagates along the cable towards the receiver port. Figure 4 depicts the frequency dependent propagation loss

Figure 3. Smoothed Shielded Effectiveness for RG-58C/U and RG-223/U.

Figure 4. Empirical Model for Transmission Loss.

for three cable types. A conservative model would assume that an ungrounded port connection may have an exposed center conductor. Then the coupling at the receiver could be characterized by the bare wire current with some loss due to propagation along the cable.

The shielding model in IEMCAP uses both of these coupling mechanisms. IEMCAP calculates the attenuation of coupled power due to a grounded, circumferentially bonded shield and the attenuation due to propagation loss from an exposed center conductor (if one is present). The attenuation factors are compared and the lower of the two is used in the program. Experimental verification of this methodology was performed and measured data agreed well with the IEMCAP predictions. Experimental verification of this methodology is depicted in figure 5. This figure is a superposition of the attenuation due to the two different mechanisms for a RG-58C/U coaxial cable. Curve 1 is the measured shielding effectiveness of the cable and curve 2 is the measured attenuation along a one-meter length of the cable. These curves depict the actual measured values of attenuation before any smoothing or bounding algorithms were applied. Curve 3 is the measured

attenuation of the same cable with an exposed center conductor one meter from the receiver port and, as can be seen from the figure, it follows the lower of curve 1 or curve 2. This result supports the attenuation model selected for use in IEMCAP. A similar set of attenuation models was developed for double shielded cables and twisted pairs.

Experimental Verification

The new IEMCAP algorithm derived from mode tuned reverberation chamber measurements was verified experimentally. Tests in an anechoic chamber showed the same sensitivity of "shielding effectiveness" to port termination condition and the lack of sensitivity to cable length, as were predicted by the model. Measurements of the coupled current into a bare wire above a ground plane, for a variety of illumination conditions, showed excellent agreement with the theoretically derived bounds for the bare wire coupling. Figure 6 compares the results of the validation test for the shielding effectiveness of an RG-223/U cable with the new IEMCAP model. It shows that the anechoic chamber measurements agree well with the IEMCAP predicted values.

Figure 5. Frequency Dependent Attenuation of Far Port Field-to-Wire Coupling.

Figure 6. Measured Shielding Effectiveness and IEMCAP Model for RG-223/U.

Code Comparisons

After the implementation and experimental verification of the new coupling algorithms, a variety of calculations were performed with the old and new algorithms to better ascertain the impact of this improvement in modeling fidelity. Figure 1 demonstrated the magnitude of changes in the prediction of the coupled current on a bare wire. At low frequencies, where the height above the ground plane is small relative to the wavelength, the old and new computations are in excellent agreement. As the frequency increases in a particular scenario, the new coupling algorithms show a saturation of the current, whereas, transmission line theory predicts a linear rise. The old IEMCAP coupling algorithms deviated from transmission line theory and

imposed a saturation level based on the coupling to a matched halfwave dipole antenna. This bound is sensitive to the wire length and can produce a limit to the coupled current that is orders of magnitude greater than that predicted by method-of-moments computations. The enhanced algorithm uses transmission line predictions for frequencies up to 1 GHz, a weighted average between the transmission line model and the new empirical model for frequencies between 1 and 3 GHz, and the empirical model predictions for frequencies above 3 GHz.

Figure 7 shows a graphical comparison of the new shielding models and the original IEMCAP models. Two features stand out in this comparison. The first is that, unlike what the user would expect, the old IEMCAP shielding models were not conservative at high

Figure 7. Shielding Effectiveness Comparison.

frequencies. The second feature is that the current data shows that the single and double shielded cables are equally effective at high frequencies and they approach each other at the higher frequencies, which is representative of actual measurements. This suggests a thru-the-shield coupling mechanism that saturates as the shield optical coverage decreases (when expressed in terms of wavelength).

When these features of the bare wire coupling and the "shielding effectiveness" are combined in the IEMCAP formalism, the EMC analyst is presented with interference margins that can differ by 25 dB. Figure 8 shows a representative comparison of the new and old IEMCAP environmental field coupling predictions. The new computations are usually less conservative than the old transmission line based algorithms. Differences of 10 dB are routine and differences of 25 dB are not hard to find at high frequencies. An examination of line length and

termination condition can highlight the cases where large modeling differences would be expected.

New Code Options

The new version of IEMCAP provides four new options, which consist of an out-of-band representation of port termination impedance, a user selected flag for the presence of an exposed center conductor, a statistical confidence factor flag, and wire propagation characteristics. Port impedance options can be selected to allow modeling of parasitic capacitive and inductive effects for frequencies above 1 GHz. These options only effect the field-to-wire calculations. The next option is for an exposed center conductor. If the exposed center conductor flag is set, all shielding effectiveness above 1 GHz is negated. A statistical confidence factor option can be invoked to allow the standard deviation of the mode tuned reverberation chamber measurements to be

Figure 8. Comparison of IEMCAP Interference Results.

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incorporated into the coupled current predictions. It allows unshielded wires to have a 5 dB increase in coupled current and shielded cables to have a 10 dB increase. The final option selects the cable type, which invokes the specific transmission loss model for that cable type. The cable types that can be selected include: RG-58, RG-59, RG-223, shielded twisted pair and double shielded twisted pair.

Summary

The enhanced field-to-wire algorithm developed for IEMCAP, to cover the frequency range from 1 Gz to 40 Gz, has been described in this paper. The empirical models were derived from a series of experimental measurements performed in a mode tuned chamber and from the bounding behavior of bare wire coupling currents as characterized by method-of-moments calculations. The algorithm is implemented in a modular manner and provides a smooth transition with the previous low

frequency IEMCAP predictions. A comparison of the field-to-wire calculations between the previous and new versions of IEMCAP was made and the superiority of the new model was demonstrated. These modifications provide the EMC analyst with increased confidence in the high frequency field-to-wire calculations performed by IEMCAP.

References

- [1] J. Bogdanor, R. Pearlman, and M. Siegal, "Intrasystem Electromagnetic Compatibility Analysis Program," RADC-TR-74-342, Vol. I and Vol. II, Rome Air Development Center, December 1974.
- [2] P. Griffin, A. McMahon, G. Capraro, S. Macris, and J. Riccardi, "SHF/EHF Field-to-Wire Coupling Models," RADC-TR-88-151, Final Technical Report, Rome Air Development Center, July 1988.